

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF PERSONAL MANAGEMENT IN THE ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

Bazarova Mamlakat Supiyevna

Senior Lecturer, Department of Economics,
International University of Asia

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Abstract. *Personnel Management is a continuous process, aimed at purposefully changing the motivation of people in order to increase their maximum level of performance and, accordingly, achieve high final results.*

Keyword: *bank management, cash register, Banking Technologies, comprehensive management of labor resources promote quality work of innovative management.*

ОТЛИЧИТЕЛЬНЫЕ ЧЕРТЫ ПЕРСОНАЛЬНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ

Аннотация. *Управление персоналом представляет собой непрерывный процесс, направленный на целенаправленное изменение мотивации людей с целью повышения их максимального уровня производительности и, соответственно, достижения высоких конечных результатов.*

Ключевые слова: *банковский менеджмент, кассовый аппарат, банковские технологии, комплексное управление трудовыми ресурсами способствуют качественной работе инновационного менеджмента.*

Bank management, on the basis of which, first of all, lies the skill of being able to work with people, therefore, one of the important components of the innovative management of banks is Personnel Management. It is no secret that the quality of human resources depends on their contribution to the implementation of the goals facing the bank, as well as the quality of banking activities in many ways on the effective way of working with employees.

The formation of a two-stage banking system, its structural refinement, as well as the creation of an electronic payment system are the main features of new structures in places: Uzbek choosing in accordance, it is necessary to create a unified system of accounting for all types of awards. It is worth saying that Personnel Management is causing much wider controversy in our domestic literature, since the relevance of this direction of improving banking activity is also gaining confirmation in the experience of foreign banks, which have experienced the negative consequences of this problem.

There are different approaches to defining the problem of Personnel Management, methods for solving it. While some scientists describe in their articles the management of an internal firm as the sum of the principles, methods and means of managing the resources of an organization with the aim of achieving the highest efficiency and utility, they show the individual qualities of employees as a resource. It is generally not appropriate to treat employees as same-sex substations, with each employee having specific values and motives. Personnel Management is a continuous process, the maximum number of people In our opinion, by personnel management it is necessary to carry out three strategic tasks.

1. Ensuring the necessary specialization and level of qualification for the rapid and complete satisfaction of the bank's contributions to labor resources.

2. To create conditions for employees to perform the functions assigned to them at the highest level of efficiency.

3. The creation of a comprehensive system of Personnel Management aimed at ensuring the necessary level of interaction of the system with other directions and elements of banking management.

Accordingly, the Personnel Management System is always made up of three interacting blocks. These are: management strategy, managed subsystems, a block that provides the overall functioning of the system. Banking Personal Management Strategy refers to the sum of conceptual approaches to the implementation of the general tasks of Personnel Management. By controlled subsystems.

- complex control system
- Organization of rational use of personnel content on the basis of determining the capacity and capabilities of the employee, planning his growth in the service;
- training and retraining of personnel, professional development;
- remuneration of Labor, improvement of other types of Labor motivation, in accordance with the contribution of each employee to the general work.

This concept includes the following principles:

1. To optimize the number of employees in each department.
2. Selection of employees whose qualifications and individual capabilities correspond to the work performed.
3. Maximum automation of Labor and the use of Information Technology.
4. To exclude duplication of functions.
5. Saving working time.
6. Creation of the necessary socio-domestic conditions.

Formation of personnel reserves, candidates for leadership in the development of regulatory and methodological documents, selection of specialists for key positions, study Effective management system of Commercial Banking Personnel. The concept of working with employees in a commercial bank can be built on the basis of interactions between its main mechanisms:

- personnel planning and forecasting;
- selection and allocation of personnel;
- staff assessment;
- professional development of employees;
- motivation of employees.

Thus, based on the job model, a complete list of requirements for a job candidate will be developed. The list includes the following elements:

- accounting data (age, gender, etc.k., i.e. information contained in a personal leaflet, autobiography, recommendations, work book, etc.); qualification level (education, specialty, where he studied and advanced his qualifications after receiving a diploma);

- professional knowledge in banking, economics, finance, management, psychology, programs, foreign language, etc;
- professional skills (working with people, regulations, methodical - work experience (by Specialty, Financial and credit, seniority in the banking system, participation in public affairs);
- personal-psychological qualities (honesty, hard work, accessibility, discipline, mental potential, resistance to overwork and stress, etc.k.);
- working conditions (work room, telephone, transport, computer equipment, educational and methodological Center, Library);
- remuneration and social benefits (salary of office, Masters, Awards, monthly compensation payments, labor leave, anniversary dates, material assistance in cases of death of loved ones, natural disasters and accidents, insurance, preferential travel, granting additional leave, the use of physical education-wellness complexes, the appointment of an additional pension). The scope of managerial influence of managerial tasks in the description of the place of work of the leader, responsibility for decisions made, uniformity of work performed, scope of planning, coordination.

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